

A Portrait of Woman in the Novels of Kamala Markandaya: A Review

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Novel is very extensively used and appreciated genre by modern writers. Presently, it has become the dominant literary form all over the world. Hence, 'wherever literacy has spread the novel - realistic, precise, this-wordly - has swiftly followed. 'The Art of Fiction' as Henry James reverently called it, is not reserved for a few initiates. The modern world demands film and television programmes. Indeed it is only through the novel that literature, the unglamorous written word without colour or illustration, is able to compete with its brash competitors of the screen.'¹ Indian English novel is also glorified by the notable Indian novelists like Nayantara Sahgal, Bharati Mukharji, Kamala Surayya, Mahashweta Devi, Kamala Markandaya etc. The novels written by Indian woman novelist will be the best source to understand the exact condition of women in Indian social and family scenario. Many women novelists have explored the ethical and spiritual predicament of woman in their novels and showed their endeavors to face the challenges of life to achieve a complete harmony in family relations. These writers have created their own recognition in Indian Literature in English by keeping honesty with the art of fiction. According to K.R.S. Iyengar 'Women are the natural story-tellers even when they don't write or publish.'² A women can express the plight of a woman more effectively. Actually, 'Woman was easily caught in the meshes of intrigue, and social taboos of all kinds and her subservience to man gave her very little freedom of action. Yet she managed to endure somehow, by sheer power of her womanliness – her gifts of beauty, love, patience, compassion and goodness'.³

However, this is a simple attempt to take a short review of the female characters in the novels of Kamala Markandaya who is popular for her honest and realistic inscription of the female characters. She was born on 23 June 1924 into an upper middle class family. Kamala Markandaya has a comprehensive sensibility for female psychology, so she could have boldly explored each and every aspect of female personality in her novels. She emphasizes that a woman is not lower and inferior to man but she plays a fundamental role in upholding the holiness of her family. Markandaya's women have given a ray of hope to others and encourage the women who are isolated, frustrated and dominated. Kamala Markandaya wants her women should come out of their disappointed and frustrated life. Markandaya has encouraged the women and their feminine sensibility and brought them into life by defining their problems. The women characters in kamala Markandaya's novels possess the extraordinary life affirming qualities. The characters like Rukmani, Anusaya, Helen, Jayamma, Nalini, Mohini, Usha, Sarojini, Mirabai, Pamela, Roshan, etc. are symbol of wisdom, strength, and courage. These women characters of Markandaya are many times better than the male characters in her novels. Kamala Markandaya has very realistic approach towards the life of woman therefore it is natural that women characters are very significant in her novels. She has been called 'one of the most important Indian novelists writing in English'⁴.

Markandaya began her career as a writer with her first novel *Nectar in a Sieve* published in

1954. The popularity of this novel encouraged her for further writing. Markandaya's another novel *Two Virgins* brought her international reputation as a writer. The other novels by Markandaya are *Some Inner Fury*, *A Silence of Desire*, *Possession*, *A Handful of Rice*, *The Coffer Dams*, *The Nowhere Man*, *Two Virgins*, *The Golden Honeycomb* and *Pleasure City and Bombay Tiger*. In major of her novels Kamala Markandaya treats woman as a liberated individual in search of her real personality. These women are tender but strong to fight with the destiny. Kamala Markanday is mainly known for her writing about culture clash between urban and rural societies in India.

The novel *Nectar in a Sieve* is the reflection of an old woman named Rukmini who married Nathan at very younger age. This novel presents the social contempt for a childless woman in certain sections of Indian society, the poverty and lack of food, timid conditions of the villagers who become the victims of social and economical problems. They live permanent insecure life as Rukmani says that fear is their constant companion. They have the fear of unkind nature, hunger, and death. However, Rukmini never loses her faith in life. She fights with the nature and dreadful poverty with all her womanly strength and will power. She sacrifices all her savings to buy food for her family. As a traditional woman, she is moved with her husband's inspiring words. She is satisfied with her simple life and always ready to work hard. Rukmini gets shock when her married daughter returns back being a barren woman because she knows better that a barren woman is always affronted by society and

sometimes discarded by her husband. Rukmani's sorrows knew no bounds when she knows her daughter; Ira has been going through a critical situation being a childless woman. She bears shocks aftershocks but never surrenders to the destiny. She accepts the realities of life and proves herself as a symbol of power. Markandaya, thus draws our attention to the fact that notwithstanding the pessimism and despair which may appear there is a strong desire for life, optimism and confidence in her women characters.

If Rukmani is significant for her courage and patience, Mirabai in *Some Inner Fury* is remarkable for her sacrifice. Mirabai is at the centre with her full feminine consciousness and creative understanding. She is enough modern but her mind does not overcome her traditional consciousness. Mira represents herself as a rebellious woman. Premala is traditional by nature and behaves in order to become a devoted wife. She loves her children and moved when looks at their pitiable condition. Premala, till the end of her life remained faithful towards her husband. But her feminine desire to be a mother remains incomplete. Her act of adopting an orphan child makes her husband that wife is not mere a property but is a woman who has her own desires.

Kamala Markandaya in *A Silence of Desire* examines the human crises, the psychological stresses and isolation. A new face of a traditional woman may be seen here in the form of Sarojini's more religiousness. Sarojini manages her family being a good wife, good mother and a good cook. Her religious nature comes out with the pictures and images of God and Goddesses in her dining room. She worships the God, visits temples and attends swami's preaching enthusiastically. Her husband Dandekar is modern in outlook but relishes the traditional image of woman. He hopes Sarojini must be traditional and faithful to him. His doubt about Sarojini's chastity creates a wide gulf in their relationship. Sarojini who values chastity gets shock when her husband calls her 'a soiled woman'. But she bears it and thinks that she is right and has done nothing wrong. She recompenses her outgoing hours by working hard and little sleep which is a common feature of a traditional woman. Sarojini is deeply hurt at the suspicious behavior of her husband but she never tries to explain it. They approximately do not speak to each other for a long time but at last, the silence is broken and the complete situations become well.

Kamala Markandaya's *Possession* deals with the story of different type of women, Anusaya and Caroline and Annabel. Anusaya is well aware of her tradition and Caroline is the true representative of the British mentality. Caroline possesses Valmiki to satisfy her personal

pleasure and takes him to England as a source of money making. She treats him well but uses him different way. Annabel is the liberated girl and truly modern. She develops a relationship with Valmiki and hopes to marry him but Caroline cannot tolerate it because Valmiki was in her possession.

Kamala Markandaya's *A Handful of Rice* reveals the cultural conflict between the two cultures. Nalini in *A Handful of Rice* is a woman who is virtuous, decent and has a perfect feminine outlook. Ravi falls in love with her and married her thinking that she will be a great supporter throughout his life. She has some common features of a traditional woman. She never complains against the exploitation by her husband. Nalini is modest humble and self-satisfied. She is a traditional wife, good sister and a good mother and being a true daughter, she looks after her father in his illness. She guides her husband and honestly supports him in his critical situation. On the contrary, Thangam is completely different type of woman. Nalini is virtuous whereas Thangam never cares for it. She never observes moralities. Thangam challenges the traditional image of woman by leaving her father alone in a wretched condition. Exactly opposite to the character of Nalini, Thangam is dishonorable, hard-hearted and selfish. Jayamma in *Handful Rice* is known as a cruel, selfish and an ungenerous woman. She is a practical woman with a great common sense and full knowledge of human psychology. She is very greedy. One night, Ravi becomes furious and beats Nalini and in the fit of anger, he rapes Jayamma. When Ravi expresses regret she boldly says him that she has forgotten that event and never cared about that. Jayamma is entirely opposite to Sarojini as regards to woman's chastity. With her dominating nature Jayamma holds her family as in a matriarchal society.

Markandaya's next novel *The Coffer Dams* is based on the internal conflicts between the oppressed and the oppressor. The arrogant British officer, Clinton is very hard-hearted whereas Helen, his wife who has a soft corner for the poor. Helen has a human deliberation and good wills for others which make her a symbol of sympathy. She wants to establish a harmonious relation between two cultures. Helen is trapped between her natural individual needs and the demands of her husband. She tried to establish human values but she had to pay a tremendous amount for that. Kamala Markandaya reveals different aspects of the image of woman by using a novel as an appropriable medium for her purpose. It can be said that through her woman characters, she has been finding herself somewhere. Kamala Markandaya is very conscious about the sexual relationship. For her, sex is not only the physical

need but it is a spiritual ceremony. She admires it, worships and loves it. It is a key to open the doors of true love that lead to the world of eternal delight. In *Two Virgins*, Kamala Markandaya draws an image of a young girl who is secretly yearning for sex. Unfortunately as the cultural limitations, sex is commonly a forbidden thing in Indian society.

In *The Golden Honeycomb* Kamala Markandaya introduces the readers to the national awakening leading to struggle against the colonizers. The characters like Manjula, Mohini and Usha have their roots in Indian tradition. These two women are used as the model of traditional womanhood. Manjula as a true patriot animates her grandson Rabi against the British rulers and arouses anti-British feelings into his mind. As a true traditional woman she is quite anxious about the future heir to continue the lineage. Manjula is rebellious; she feeds her baby herself which is against the royal customs. But she thinks that it is quite against the basic human freedom to prevent a mother from nursing her own child. Her blood is full of patriotic feelings. Manjula has sown the seeds of royal rebellion in Mohini. Bawajiraj III falls in love with Mohini and wishes to marry her and make the queen. But Mohini regards all kinds of freedom and boldly rejects his proposal of marriage by saying that she wants to be free and would not like to be a queen at the cost of her freedom. She hates every kind of slavery. Mohini wants to enjoy her life according to her own values and norms. She is really a symbol of freedom and a strong willpower. Kamala Markandaya's *Pleasure City* explores the universal relation of humanity. In this novel, she portrays different types of images of women. Mrs. Bridie is like the Mother Mary who has a lot of sympathies for poor and she is always ready to help them. She tries hard to lessen their suffering. Perhaps being childless she tries to find out some moments of pleasure in the company of these people. Valli in *Pleasure City* represents herself as a woman who is neither completely traditional nor entirely modern but at the center of both. She is conscious about her family responsibilities. Valli is cooperative and self-supported. She crosses the threshold of her home and earns money by working as a sales assistant. She boldly runs a shop and enjoys free life.

Kamala Markandaya's novels state that women are not weak to men although they are better in every field and fight boldly with challenges by taking risks. In fact, 'Kamala Markandaya's female figures are subjected to binary pulls, torn between tradition and modernity, between the desire for autonomy and emancipation, and her need for nurturance; between her duty as a daughter, a wife and a mother and her dignity as a human being'.⁵ Consequently this is a short review of Kamala

Markandaya's women characters that represent different portraits of women characters and female perception. Throughout her novels, Kamala Markandaya presents a new vision for women by creating a new strength for them. She explores some of the best aspects of the personality of a woman who has a natural influence to change the life from adversity to privilege.

References:

1. India in Fiction... by T.D Brunton from 'Critical Essays on Indian Writing in English', Ed. By M.K. Naik, Karnatak University, Dharwar. P.199
2. Iyengar K.R. Srinivasa *Indian Writing in English*, Sterling Publishers Private Limited, New Delhi. – p. 435
3. Iyengar K.R. Srinivasa *Indian Writing in English*, Sterling Publishers Private Limited, New Delhi. – p. 437
4. Citation: Marchionni, Paola (2002) "Markandaya, Kamala" In Alison Donnell (ed.) *Companion to Contemporary Black British Culture*. Routledge. pp. 192-3. ISBN 978-1-134-70025-7.
5. Sharma Nirupama's article, 'Treatment of Women...' from, Agrawal Anju Bala, *Post Independence Indian Writing in English*, Authorspress, Delhi. P.89
6. Arora Sudhir Kumar, *A Study of Kamala Markandaya's Women*, Atlantic Publishers & Distributers, New Delhi.